

STUDY SKILLS OF ARTS AND SCIENCE COLLEGE STUDENTS

J. MASTER ARUL SEKAR

Assistant Professor
Department of Education
Periyar Maniammai University
Vallam, Thanjavur
Tamil Nadu, South India.

DR. K.K. RAJENDRAN

Assistant Professor
Department of Education, CDE
Bharathidasan University
Tiruchirappalli - 620 024
Tamil Nadu, South India.

Introduction

Education is essentially a vital human activity and is considered as the most rewarding investment. Therefore it is rightly said that the progress of a country, particularly of a democratic country, depends upon the quality of its system of education in general and higher education in particular. Higher Education is called as a long-term social investment in the promotion of economic growth, culture, social cohesion, equality and justice. Higher Education should be individualized and personalized to the utmost and should constitute a preparation for self-learning of the college students. There will always be a deep and wide chasm between what one knows and what ought to be known and nothing can bridge this gap better than original thinking and capacity to learn aided by careful and well planned study.

Significance of the study

Study skills are very important in helping students to learn and achieve good gadgets. According to Merriam-Webster's Online Dictionary (2007), the study skills are the application of the mental faculties to the acquisition of knowledge. It is the ability of any learner to study successfully that depends to a great extent on his fundamental study skills, namely his ability to concentrate, to perceive correctly and accurately, as well as the ability to remember what has been perceived. The study skills are the cognitive

skills amenable to manipulation and improvement through cognitive training. To be a good student, it is necessary to be able to read, memorise and write fastly and effectively. It has been researched and suggested that learning or study skills of college students could benefit from using these several skills with necessary intelligence. The researcher attempts to gain valuable insight into the study skills of arts and science college students.

Objectives of the study

1. To find out the level of study skills of arts and science college students.
2. To find out whether there is any significant difference between men and women students of arts and science colleges in their study skills.
3. To find out whether there is any significant difference between arts group and science group students of arts and science colleges in their study skills.
4. To find out whether there is any significant difference between undergraduate and postgraduate students of arts and science colleges in their study skills.
5. To find out whether there is any significant difference between rural and urban arts and science college students in their study skills.

Null Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference between men and women students of arts and science colleges in their study skills.
2. There is no significant difference between arts group and science group students of arts and science colleges in their study skills.
3. There is no significant difference between undergraduate and postgraduate students of arts and science colleges in their study skills.
4. There is no significant difference between rural and urban arts and science college students in their study skills.

Methodology

The investigator adopted survey method. The population for the present study consists of students who are studying in the arts and science colleges of Tiruchirappali District of Tamil Nadu State, South India.

The investigator has used stratified random sampling technique for collecting the data. The stratification is made on the basis of gender, subject and degree of the college students and the location of colleges. The sample consists of 216 students from two Government arts and science colleges in Tiruchirappalli District of Tamil Nadu State, South India. Among them 108 are men students and 108 are women students.

Study Skills Check List developed and standardized by Virginia University, Australia (2006) is used. Mean, standard deviation, 't' test are used in the present study as statistical technique.

Analysis of Data

Table-1

Level of study skills of arts and science college students

Study Skills	Low		Moderate		High	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Time Scheduling	8	3.7	135	62.5	73	33.8
Concentration	11	5.1	160	74.1	45	20.8
Listening and Note Taking	44	20.4	171	79.2	1	0.5
Reading Skill	1	0.5	205	94.9	10	4.6
Preparation of Examination	1	0.5	214	99.7	1	0.5
Writing Skill	43	19.9	130	60.2	43	19.9
Study Skills (General)	5	2.3	209	96.8	2	0.9

It is inferred from the above table that 3.7% of arts and science college students have low, 62.5% of them have moderate and 33.8% of them have high level of time scheduling. It is learnt from the table that 5.1% of arts and science college students have low, 74.1% of them have moderate and 20.8% of them have high level of concentration. It is also inferred from the table that 20.4% of arts and science college students have low, 79.2% of them have moderate and 0.5% of them have high level of listening and note-taking. It is understood from the table that 0.5% of arts and science college students have low, 94.9% of them have moderate and 4.6% of them have high level of reading skill. It is learnt from the table that 0.5% of arts and science college students have low, 99.7% of them have moderate and 0.5% of them have high level of preparation of examination.

The table shows that 19.9% of arts and science college students have low, 60.2% of them have moderate and 19.9% of them have high level of writing skill. In general, it is understood that 2.3% of arts and science college students have low, 96.8% of them have moderate and 0.9% of them have high level of study skills.

Null Hypothesis-1

There is no significant difference between men and women students of arts and science colleges in their study skills.

Table-2

Difference between men and women students of arts and science colleges in their study skills

Study Skills	Men (N=108)		Women (N=108)		Calculated 't' value	Remarks at 5% level
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Time Scheduling	5.10	0.76	5.21	0.74	1.081	Not Significant
Concentration	4.83	0.81	4.92	0.76	0.859	Not Significant
Listening and Note Taking	4.59	0.98	4.36	1.11	1.616	Not Significant
Reading Skill	8.59	1.44	8.98	1.52	0.320	Not Significant
Preparation of Examination	4.42	1.02	4.53	1.06	0.782	Not Significant
Writing Skill	4.41	1.03	4.67	1.00	1.871	Not Significant
Study Skills (General)	32.28	3.26	32.69	2.74	0.993	Not Significant

(At 5% level of significance, the table value of 't' is 1.96)

From the above table it is inferred that there is no significant difference between men and women students of arts and science colleges in their time scheduling, concentration, listening and note-taking, reading skill, preparation of examination and writing skill, because the calculated 't' values 1.081, 0.859, 1.616, 0.320, 0.782, 1.871 are less than the table value 1.96 at 5% level of significance. In general there is no significant difference between men and women students of arts and science colleges in their study skills, as the calculated 't' value 0.993 is less than the table value 1.96 at 5% level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted.

Null Hypothesis-2

There is no significant difference between arts group and science group students of arts and science colleges in their study skills.

Table-3

Difference between arts group and science group students of arts and science colleges in their study skills

Study Skills	Arts Group (N=110)		Science Group (N=104)		Calculate d 't' value	Remarks at 5% level
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Time Scheduling	5.04	0.75	5.27	0.73	2.240	Significant
Concentration	4.78	0.73	4.98	0.83	1.859	Not Significant
Listening and Note Taking	4.30	0.98	4.66	1.10	2.538	Significant
Reading Skill	9.02	1.31	8.86	1.64	0.787	Not Significant
Preparation of Examination	4.58	1.04	4.37	1.03	1.444	Not Significant
Writing Skill	4.46	1.02	4.63	1.02	1.210	Not Significant
Study Skills (General)	32.20	3.29	32.79	2.67	1.447	Not Significant

(At 5% level of significance, the table value of 't' is 1.96)

From the above table it is learnt that there is significant difference between arts group and science group students of arts and science colleges in their time scheduling and listening and note-taking, as the calculated 't' values 2.240 and 2.538 are greater than the table value 1.96 at 5% level of significance. But there is no significant difference between arts group and science group students of arts and science colleges in their concentration, reading skill, preparation of examination and writing skill, as the calculated 't' values 1.859, 0.787, 1.444 and 1.210 are less than the table value 1.96 at 5% level of significance. In general there is no significant difference between arts group and science group students of arts and science colleges in their study skills, as the calculated 't' value 0.993 is less than the table value 1.96 at 5% level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted.

Null Hypothesis-3

There is no significant difference between undergraduate and postgraduate students of arts and science colleges in their study skills.

Table-4

Difference between undergraduate and postgraduate students of arts and science colleges in their study skills

Study Skills	Undergraduate (N=110)		Postgraduate (N=106)		Calculated 't' value	Remarks at 5% level
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Time Scheduling	5.09	0.73	5.22	0.77	1.320	Not Significant
Concentration	4.75	0.82	5.00	0.73	2.390	Significant
Listening and Note Taking	4.50	1.05	4.45	1.06	0.327	Not Significant
Reading Skill	9.21	1.46	8.66	1.45	2.753	Significant
Preparation of Examination	4.74	0.96	4.20	1.05	3.913	Significant
Writing Skill	4.70	0.83	4.37	1.16	2.406	Significant
Study Skills (General)	33.01	2.40	31.94	3.47	2.655	Significant

(At 5% level of significance, the table value of 't' is 1.96)

There exists no significant difference between the undergraduate and postgraduate students of arts and colleges in their time scheduling and listening and note-taking, because the calculated 't' values 1.320 and 0.327 are lower than the table value 1.96 at 5% level of significance. Whereas, there is a significant difference between the undergraduate and postgraduate students of arts and science colleges in their concentration, reading skill, preparation of examination and writing skills, as the calculated 't' values 2.390, 2.753, 3.913 and 2.406 are greater than the table value 1.96 at 5% level of significance. In general there is significant difference between undergraduate and postgraduate students of arts and science colleges in their study skills, as the

calculated 't' value 2.655 is greater than the table value 1.96 at 5% level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected.

Null Hypothesis-4

There is no significant difference between rural and urban arts and science college students in their study skills.

Table-5

Difference between rural and urban arts and science college students in their study skills

Study Skills	Rural (N=112)		Urban (N=104)		Calculated 't' value	Remarks at 5% level
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Time Scheduling	5.03	0.72	5.28	0.77	2.487	Significant
Concentration	4.78	0.76	4.98	0.81	1.818	Not Significant
Listening and Note Taking	4.47	0.90	4.53	1.19	0.825	Not Significant
Reading Skill	9.14	1.27	8.74	1.66	2.003	Significant
Preparation of Examination	4.68	0.94	4.25	1.09	3.071	Significant
Writing Skill	4.51	0.95	4.57	1.09	0.423	Not Significant
Study Skills (General)	32.58	2.75	32.38	3.28	0.497	Not Significant

(At 5% level of significance, the table value of 't' is 1.96)

From the above table, it is understood that there is no significant difference between urban and rural arts and science college students in their concentration, reading skill and writing skill, as the calculated 't' values 1.818, 0.825 and 0.423 are less than the table value 1.96 at 5% level of significance. But there is significant difference between the students of urban and rural arts and science colleges in their time scheduling, reading skills and preparation of examination, as the calculated 't' values 2.487, 2.003 and 3.071 are greater than the table value 1.96 at 5% level of significance. In general there is no significant difference between the students of urban and rural arts and science colleges

in their study skills, as the calculated 't' value 0.497 is lower than the table 1.96 at 5% level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted.

Findings

1. The percentage analysis results reveal that 2.3% of arts and science college students have low, 96.8% of them have moderate and 0.9% of them have high level of study skills.
2. There is no significant difference between men and women students of arts and science colleges in their study skills.
3. There is no significant difference between arts group and science group students of arts and science colleges in their study skills.
4. There is significant difference between undergraduate and postgraduate students of arts and science colleges in their study skills. The undergraduate students of arts and science colleges are better in their study skills than the postgraduate students of arts and science colleges.
5. There is no significant difference between the students of urban and rural arts and science colleges in their study skills.

Discussions and Conclusion

The findings of the present study reveal that majority of the arts and science college students employ study skills at moderate level. The 't' test results reveal that there is no significant difference between men and women arts and science college students in their study skills. Similarly, there is no significant difference between the students of urban and rural arts and science colleges in their study skills. The above findings of the present study is supported by the results of the investigation made by Anbuchelvan, C. and Thilagavathy, T. (2014) that there was no significant difference among higher secondary commerce students their study habits based on the gender of the students and locality of institutions. Likewise, the results of the investigation made by Rajkumar, M. and Sundararajan, M. (2012) revealed that there was no significant difference among higher secondary students in their study habits based on the gender of the students and the locality of the schools. But there is significant difference between undergraduate and

post graduate students of arts and science colleges in their study skills. While comparing the mean scores, the undergraduate students are better in their employing their study skills than the post graduate students of arts and science college students. The present study clearly shows that the study skills of arts and science college students could benefit them with the powerful guidance from the teachers for organizing, thinking and learning. In this, the mastering of these several study skills for studying and learning by the students increases their self-efficacy and empower them to change their approach and different study strategies.

References

- Aggarwal, J. C. (2001), Theories and principles of Education, Vikas publishing House Pvt. Ltd. Delhi.
- Aggarwal, J. C. (2007), Essentials of Educational Psychology, Second Edition, Vikas Publishing House Pvt. Ltd., Noida.
- Anbuchelvan, C. and Thilagavathy, T. (2014), Achievement in Commerce in Relation to Study habit, Indian Journal of Applied Research, Vol. 4, No.1, PP 165-166.
- Anderson, G. and Arsenault, N. (1998), Fundamental of Educational Research, Taylor & Fransis, London and New York.
- John W. Best (1997), Research in Education, Prentice Hall of India Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi.
- Kothari C. R. (2000), Research Methodology, Wishwa Prakashan Pvt. Ltd. New Delhi.
- Kulbir Sighu (1985), Methodology of research in Education, Sterling Publishers Pvt. Ltd. New Delhi.
- Lucy Hearne (2008), Study Skills for Undergraduate Students, Waterford Institute of Technology, Waterford: WIT.
- Mangal S. K. (2005), Statistics in Psychology and Education, Hall Indian Pvt. Ltd. New Delhi.
- Nagaraju, M.T.V. (2006), Study Habits of Secondary School Students, Discovery Publishing House, New Delhi-110002.
- Prem Prakash (2006), Essentials of Psychology, P.P. Publishers, Virudhunagar-620001.

Rajkumar, M. and Soundarajan, M. (2012), A study on higher secondary students study habit in Tirunelveli district, Indian Society for Education and Environment, Indian J. Innovations Dev., Vol.1, No. 4.

Sandra Kerka (2007), Study Skills, What works: Evidence-based strategies for youth practitioners, Learning work Connection, The Ohio State University, Columbus, OH 43210.

Stella Cottrell (2003), The Study Skills Hand Book, Hampshire: Palgrave Macmillan, New York-10010.